

DEMOCRACY, SOCIAL JUSTICE AND INDIGENESHIP QUESTION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper examined the impact of indigeneship on social justice and democratic governance in Nigeria. The paper noted that the issue of indigeneship recognition implicates peaceful co-existence, national integration, national unity, and democratic norms. It observed that the issues surrounding indigeneship can be traced to the 1999 Constitution, which laid out the process and procedure required to obtain citizenship but failed to specify the guidelines for the acquisition of indigeneship, even when several provisions of the constitution refer to the term. The paper posited that this inherent constitutional gap is unhealthy for a federal system where people from different ethnic groups live together to pursue their individual goals and aspirations. It stated that a proper understanding of the nature and limits of indigeneship is pivotal to promoting inclusiveness and equal participation in the allocation of state resources. It recommended that the 1999 Constitution should be amended to include the definition of indigene to enable states and local government authorities to establish appropriate guidelines on the acquisition of indigeneship and diffuse the tension associated with the indigene/settler dichotomy. It also recommended that Government should constantly launch public awareness programs to inform the general public, in particular traditional leaders and important local stakeholders, about the need to coexist peacefully with members of different ethnic groups without engaging in any form of discriminatory tendencies.

Keywords: *Constitution, Democracy, Equality, Indigenes, Indigeneship, Social, Justice, and Nigeria.*

1.0.Introduction:

The spirit of the constitution is to ensure that every Nigerian citizen notwithstanding where he originates from is entitled to socio-political benefits in the country. He is considered to be equal to his fellow citizens and may have equal access and opportunity to socio-political benefits and resources in the country. This is without discrimination of any sort. the constitution expressly affirms that nobody must be discriminated against in any part of the country based on the circumstances of his or her sex, state of origin, place of birth, etc. However, the same constitution affirms the rights of indigenous people to protection from extinction and domination. For instance, the constitution recognizes the right of every community in Nigeria to equal representation and enjoyment of privileges in public services and welfare amenities. The paper takes a look at various areas of apparent conflicts between indigeneship and citizenship. It noted that while government legislations are aimed at ensuring balance among the diverse ethnic nationalities in the country, it is submitted that the implementation of some of those legislations often runs contrary to the ideal of democracy and the socio-justice they pretend to preserve. The discussion further suggests that indigeneship runs contrary to the ideal of citizenship which every Nigerian is reckoned with and the governance is built and operated on the principle of egalitarianism. Indigeneship creates favoritism, unjustified discrimination, and disunity and as such it tends to fan the embers of discord in a multi-ethnic, religious, and multicultural society like Nigeria.

The paper calls for caution in the making and implementation of laws and policies that can be counterproductive to the ideal of good governance and national integration. The paper also suggests an amendment to the 1999 Constitution to include the definition of indigene to enable states and local government authorities to establish guidelines and modalities on how to become an indigene to address the imbalance and abuses associated with the indigene/settler dichotomy. It further recommended that the government establish appropriate enforcement mechanisms to sanction those who hide under indigeneship entitlement to cause division and perpetuate injustice in society. The paper is divided into four parts: The first part introduces the subject matter and provides a general overview of the paper. The second part focuses on legal and institutional frameworks promoting indigeneship recognition in Nigeria. The third part highlights some notable examples of discriminatory tendencies of indigeneship recognition. Part four addresses the impacts of indigeneship on Nigerian democratic governance and national development. The fifth part provides the conclusion and recommendations.

2.0. Conceptual Clarification:

2.0.1. Democracy

Just like any other socio-political terms, arriving at an acceptable definition of the term “democracy” is a herculean task that may not be possible. It is very difficult to reach a consensus on the definition of democracy.¹ However, the idea of democracy was seen to have its origin in Athens in the 5th century BC.² The word “democracy” has its origin in two separate Greek words: *demos* which has been translated to mean “the people” and *kratein* or *kratos*, meaning “to rule”. Hence, the amalgamation of these two words is used in the coining of the word “democracy” which means “the rule by the people”.³ The Constitution of the Island of Rhodes was the first constitution to mention and reflect the concept of Democracy in 1641. In the said constitution, the power to legislate and supervise the enforcement of the law was in reality granted to the people.⁴ In the modern time, democracy has been adjudged as the most acceptable system of government. The system enhances the participation of the populace, ensures the operation rule of law, checks, and balances among the three arms of government, and brings about effective and efficient accountability from the government to the people. Democracy is defined as a government in which supreme power is invested in the people and exercised by them directly or indirectly through representation.⁵ In democratic governance, the supreme power and authority reside in the people though exercised through an institutionalized system of elected representation.⁶ It implies a system of government that is largely centered on the principles of popular sovereignty, social justice, political equality, equity, and the rule of law. Democracy is the most widely accepted system of government wherein the socio-political and economic powers are vested in the people, who have the ultimate right to participate in the decision-making processes that affect their lives. In a truly democratic setting therefore, people exercise their rights to participate in decision-making processes, hold their elected representative to account for their actions and inaction, enthrone the principles of the rule of law, bring about the fundamental objectives and directive principles of the state, and governance and ensure the protection of fundamental rights of every citizen of the state. The Universal Declaration on Democracy adopted by the Inter-Parliamentary on the 16th of September 1997 described democracy as a universally recognized ideal as well as a goal that is

¹ GA Nwogu ‘Democracy: Its Meaning and Dissenting Options of the Political Class in Nigeria: A Philosophical Approach’ *Journal of Education and practice* (2015) 6(4) 131.

² Victor Ehrenberg, ‘Origins of Democracy’ *Journal of Historia* [1950] 1 (4) 51.

³ G Lindell and R Scott, A Greek -English Lexicon at “A Greek – English Lexicon” at Perseus’ <www.perseus.tufts.edu/.../text?...perseus> accessed on 13 May, 2023.

⁴ Ciftiyurek S., *Democracy*, (2007) Ankara, 12

⁵ Webster’s New Encyclopedia Dictionary (Black Dog and Leventhal Publishers 1993).

⁶ HA Aluko and F Ogunjimi, *Democracy and Administration of Social Justice in Nigeria: A Critical Assessment of the Fourth Republic*’ *Open Journal of Political Science* (2022) 12, 181.

based on common values shared by people throughout the world community irrespective of cultural, political, and economic differences. It is thus a fundamental right of citizenship to be exercised under the conditions of freedom, equality, transparency, and responsibility with due respect for the plurality of views and in the interest of the polity.⁷ The principle of democracy is founded on respect for the rule of law and human rights including equality of everyone before the law.⁸ Equality implies that everyone should be treated equally without any form of discrimination based on indigene, non-indigene, or settlers. It negates discriminatory practices that tend to undermine the fundamental values of peaceful co-existence and equal participation in the allocation of available resources and opportunities.

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 is founded on the principles of freedom, equality, and justice which are the cornerstone of democratic society.⁹ In addition to these core democratic values, the Constitution under section 42 provides for the right to freedom from discrimination. It states that citizens of Nigeria of a particular community, ethnic group, place of origin, sex, religion, or political opinion shall not be subjected either expressly or practical application of any law in force, executive or administrative actions, privileges, and advantages which citizens of Nigeria of other communities, ethnic groups, place of origin, sex, religion or political opinion are not entitled to.¹⁰ In *Anzuka v Governor of Nasarawa State*¹¹ the Court of Appeal held that in considering the meaning, characteristics, and application of the provisions of section 42 of the 1999 Constitution, the following elements are evident: (a) the provisions are rigid –the words ‘shall’ in subsection (1) and “shall” in subsection (2) bear this out; (b) the words and language are not only clear and precise but the prohibition which they convey are absolute in their context; (c) it is a prohibition against discrimination on grounds of the community, ethnic group, place of origin, sex, religion or political opinion to which a citizen belongs. They must not form an obstacle to a citizen of Nigeria exercising his rights; (d) so protective are the words, too, not only in the express application of any law in force in Nigeria but also in the practical application thereof, would the provision permit a citizen to be subjected to express and also the practical application of any executive or administrative action of Government; (e) the provision not only curbs the excesses of any law or legal system but also of any executive or the administrative action of the Government; (f) “any law” is so encompassing an expression, not limiting the type of law. it applies to any system of law in Nigeria,

⁷ Universal Declaration on Democracy 1997, art. 1.

⁸ Ibid, art. 7.

⁹ 1999 Constitution, s.17(1).

¹⁰ Ibid, s. 42(1).

¹¹ (2005) 5 NWLR pt. 919 at 484-485 CA.

whether statute law, customary law, Islamic law, or common law, applicable in Nigeria which subjects a citizen to discrimination, disability, or restriction on account of any of the grounds specified in the section; and (g) section 42(1) (a) restricts both executive and administrative action of Government which exposes a citizen of Nigeria to disabilities or restrictions which other Nigerians are not made subject to. From the foregoing, it is clear that this provision can be interpreted to include actions or omissions that unduly advanced indigeneship recognition to the detriment of other members of the society. These actions may include restrictions to access to land, water, arable land for agriculture, privileges, and opportunities available that are available in the community. To these ends, the government must take appropriate measures to combat all exploitations and abuses associated with indigeneship syndrome which undermine the core values of democratic governance including the principles of equality, equity, and justice upon which the Nigerian state is founded.

2.0.2. Social Justice

The phrase ‘social justice’ is a normative concept that involves the allocation of resources and opportunities based on the principles of equity, fairness, and equal participation.¹² It connotes equitable distribution and redistribution of material and moral resources among individuals, groups, and ethnic nationalities within a society¹³ Social justice encompasses the comprehensive allocation of entities to individuals while taking into cognizance the interdependence between those entities and the procedures for resource allocation.¹⁴ The concept of social justice is deeply rooted in Rawls’s philosophy of justice.¹⁵ Rawls defined justice as fairness. He opined that the primary goal of justice is to ensure that individual rights and duties are distributed by state authorities having regard to the various competing interests in society.¹⁶ Unlike justice, social justice is a contemporary principle that evolved from the concerns surrounding the Industrial Revolution and the desire to reconcile individual interests and social interest for the common good of society.¹⁷ The objective of social justice includes inclusive economic development, socio-cultural integration, equality of rights and duties, civic engagement, ethnic tolerance, and political

¹² Mana Khechen, *Social Justice: Concepts, Principles, Tools and Challenges*, Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia (New York 2013).

¹³ Subhash Shukla, ‘Social Justice in India: Constitutional Vision and Thereafter’ *Indian Journal of Political Science* (2015) LXXIV (2) 357-368.

¹⁴ Williams Galson, *Justice and the Human Good* (1980).

¹⁵ John Rawls, *A Theory of Justice* (Harvard University Press 1971).

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ International Forum for Social Development, *Social Justice in an Open World: The role of the United Nations* (United Nations 2006).

participation. It seeks to address issues surrounding the inequalities of distribution of income, distribution of assets, opportunities for work and employment, distribution of knowledge, health services and social security, and civic and political participation.¹⁸ It ensures that the underprivileged, vulnerable, and disabled members of society are adequately represented in the distribution of state resources, benefits, and opportunities.

Social justice is not a blind principle and a preposterous dogma. It seeks to do justice to all citizens, groups, and nationalities within the context of equality and equity.¹⁹ The principle of equality is integral to social justice. It implies a state of being equal in rights, opportunities, privileges, and status.²⁰ It seeks to ensure that individual members of society have equal access to the privileges and opportunities to live and realize their potential and contribute to national development.²¹ The principle of social justice is an integral component of democratization and democratic governance. Democracy is founded on certain normative values and principles. They include popular sovereignty, rule of law, protection of fundamental rights and freedoms, separation of power, periodic and regular elections, free and fair elections, and responsible and accountable government. These democratic values are necessary for the realization of social justice. There is a strong nexus between democracy and social justice. In liberal democracies, social justice cannot be realized without the existence of democratic institutions. These institutions provide the necessary frameworks and structures for the realization of social justice. Some social democrats have argued that social justice is a pre-condition for democracy.²² They believed that democracy and social justice are two sides of the same coin because social justice requires democracy just as democracy requires social justice.²³ This interdependence is contained in the provision of Sections 14, 15, and 17 of the 1999 Constitution under section 14 (1). It stated thus:

14 (1) The Federal Republic of Nigeria shall be a State based on the principles of democracy and social justice.

(2) It is hereby, accordingly, declared that:

¹⁸ Ibid.

¹⁹ Otega Okinono and Okpan, Samuel Okpanocha, 'Social Justice in Nigeria: Exploring the Dialectics of Good Governance and Social Economic Development', *LAPAI International Journal of Management and Social Sciences* (2020) 12 (1) <https://unidel.edu.ng/cms/uploads/publications/unidel_pub_1680705051.pdf> accessed 19 May 2023.

²⁰ Merriam Webster, Equity vs Equality: What is the Difference? <<https://www.merriam-webster.com/words-at-play/equality-vs-equity-difference>> accessed 17 March 2023.

²¹ Equality and Human Rights Commission, 'Understanding Equality' <<https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/en/secondary-education-resources/useful-information/understanding-equality>> accessed 17 March 2023.

²² Jeffery Goldfarb, 'Democracy and Social Justice' *Public Seminar* (11 March 2021).

²³ Bob Brecher, 'Introduction Democracy and Social Justice' *Studies in Social Justice* (2011) 5 (2) 145-147.

(a) sovereignty belongs to the people of Nigeria from whom government through this Constitution derives all its powers and authority;

(2) (c) the participation of the people in their government shall be ensured by the provisions of this Constitution.

(3) The composition of the Government of the Federation or any of its agencies and the conduct of its affairs shall be carried out in such a manner as to reflect the federal character of Nigeria and the need to promote national unity, and also to command national loyalty, thereby ensuring that there shall be no predominance of persons from a few State or from a few ethnic or other sectional groups in that Government or any of its agencies.

(4) The composition of the Government of a State, a local government council, or any of the agencies of such Government or council, and the conduct of the affairs of the Government or council or such agencies shall be carried out in such manner as to recognize the diversity of the people within its area of authority and the need to promote a sense of belonging and loyalty among all the people of the Federation”.

15(4) The State shall foster a feeling of belonging and of involvement among the various people of the Federation, to the end that loyalty to the nation shall override sectional loyalties/

17. (1) The State social order is founded on ideals of Freedom, Equality, and Justice.

(2) In furtherance of the social order

(a) Every citizen shall have equality of rights, obligations, and opportunities before the law;

(b) the sanctity of the human person shall be recognised and human dignity shall be maintained and enhanced;

(c) governmental actions shall be humane;

(d) exploitation of human or natural resources in any form whatsoever for reasons, other than the good of the community, shall be prevented; and

(e) the independence, impartiality, and integrity of courts of law and easy accessibility thereto shall be secured and maintained.

(3.) The State shall direct its policy towards ensuring that

(a) all citizens, without discrimination on any group whatsoever, have the opportunity for securing adequate means of livelihood as well as adequate opportunity to secure suitable employment;

(b) conditions of work are just and humane, and that there are adequate facilities for leisure and for social, religious, and cultural life;

(c) the health, safety, and welfare of all persons in employment are safeguarded and not endangered or abused;

(d) there are adequate medical and health facilities for all persons;

(e) there is equal pay for equal work without discrimination on account of sex, or on any other ground whatsoever;

(f) children, young persons, and the age are protected against any exploitation whatsoever, and against moral and material neglect;

(g) provision is made for public assistance in deserving cases or other conditions of need; and

(h) The evolution and promotion of family life is encouraged

These provisions presuppose that every Nigerian citizen has the right to equally participate in and benefit from their country's governance, particularly concerning the distribution of resources. The relationship between democracy and social justice has also been established under international law in addition to these constitutional provisions. For instance, the Copenhagen Declaration and Programme of Action adopted by the World Summit for Social Development in 1995, reinforces the need for members of the United Nations to promote democratic values and social justice. The Declaration mandates states to promote democracy, human dignity, social justice, and solidarity at the national, regional, and international levels, ensure tolerance, non-violence, pluralism, and non-discrimination, with full respect for diversity within and among societies.²⁴

From the above provisions, it is clear that the principles of democracy and social justice are not blind concepts and preposterous dogmas. They are established to promote certain fundamental objectives and ensure every citizen is treated equally and equitably irrespective of their status, position, race, and affiliation. These democratic values are deeply entrenched in the constitutions of countries and international human rights instruments including the Charter of the United Nations, the Universal Declaration on Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the Programme of Action of the United Nations General Assembly, and the United Nations Millennium Development Goals. Essentially, social justice is aimed at promoting equality of rights and opportunities among the people. The concept of equality can be classified as follows;

(a) Equality of rights

This implies that the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals must be respected without any form of discrimination. Equality of rights remained the foremost among all the categories of equality. Article 1 of the UDHR provides that “all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights”.²⁵ This position is further reaffirmed by the provisions of Article 2 to the effect that “everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms outlined in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, color, sex, language, religion, political or another opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or another status.”²⁶ The principle of equality is also enshrined in the preamble to the African Charter of Human and Peoples’ Rights. It states that “freedom, equality, justice, and dignity are essential objectives for the achievement of the legitimate aspirations of the African peoples”.²⁷ Article 2 specifically protects the

²⁴ Ibid, para. 26 (f).

²⁵ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, art.1

²⁶ Ibid, art. 2.

²⁷ African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights, 1981.

rights and freedoms guaranteed in the charter without any discrimination based on race, ethnic group, colour, sex, language, religion, political or any other opinion, national and social origin, fortune, birth, or any status.²⁸

(b) Equality of opportunities:

This implies the equality of all individuals to available opportunities and benefits in society. Equal opportunities require that everyone have access to a stable socio-economic, cultural, and political environment to enable them to realize their full potential and contribute maximally to the development of society. For example, paragraph 28 (g) of the Copenhagen Declaration and Programme of Action mandates states to adopt appropriate measures to promote equitable distribution of resources including greater access to available opportunities and benefits.²⁹ The Declaration also seeks to protect weaker and underprivileged sections of society by ensuring that their interest is properly protected in the implementation of social development policies and programmes of government. Equality of rights and opportunities implies that every citizen has access to the socio-political and economic opportunities in the country, without discrimination of any kind. However, the challenge of using indigeneship rather than citizenship as the basis to access these opportunities has created many arguments and controversies among elites and informed citizens of the country. Many people viewed the consideration of indigeneship as erroneous diversionary, discriminatory, and unwarranted in a democratic setting where social justice ought to prevail. Nigeria is a multi-ethnic and diverse culture and different backgrounds have employed the recognition of indigeneship to ensure that all segments of the society are not only carried along but have equal access to socio-political benefits and welfare resources.

2.0.3. Indigeneship

The word ‘indigeneship’ is difficult to define due to the continued migration of people across culture and space.³⁰ However, some scholars and institutions have attempted to proffer some definitions. According to the World Bank Indigenous Peoples are distinct social and cultural groups that share collective ancestral ties to the lands and natural resources where they live, occupy, or from which they have been displaced which they depend are inextricably linked to their identities, cultures, livelihoods, as well as their physical

²⁸ Ibid, art. 2.

²⁹ Ibid, para 26(g),

³⁰ OA Abimbola, and O Akin, Indigeneship and Citizenship in Nigeria: Myth and Reality’ *The Journal of Pan African Studies* (2009) 2 (9) 151-165.

and spiritual well-being.³¹ A person may be described as an indigene if he is a native of a place.³² The identity of a person is also a function of the primordial settlement in a place. The United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People 2007, does not define who an indigene is but emphasizes the need to protect the inherent right of indigenous people which is derived from their political, economic, and social structures and their cultures, spiritual traditions, histories, and philosophies, especially their rights to their lands, territories, and resources.³³ It also emphasized that respect for indigenous knowledge, culture, and practices contributes to sustainable and equitable development and proper development of the environment. There are fundamental differences between indigeneship and citizenship. Whereas indigeneship establishes a natural connection between a person and his ancestral home through a blood lineage or genealogy, citizenship is a systematic arrangement by the state to confer certain rights and privileges to certain individuals within a geographical location.³⁴ While the 1999 Constitution expressly provides for the types of citizens inducing the process and procedures of acquiring the same, it failed to define who an indigene is. In Nigeria, this indigene/settler syndrome is a major cause of ethnic/regional conflict in the quest for the just and equitable distribution of resources and may lead to a scramble and struggle for the acquisition of political power, especially when such minority ethnic group feels marginalized and neglected in the distribution of political power. The focus of this write-up is to further interrogate the extent to which indigeneship considerations are recognized and given effect in the country's socio-economic and political affairs, including the distribution and access to political offices and economic resources. This constitutional lacuna has further aggravated the indigene/settler polarization in the country.

3.0. Legal and Institutional Frameworks Promoting Indigeneship in Nigeria

The legal frameworks promoting indigeneship in Nigeria include:

3.0.1. The 1999 Constitution

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (henceforth referred to as the 1999 Constitution) does not define indigeneship, even though the word appears in several sections of the Constitution. While the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria does not clearly define the meaning of Indigeneship, it refers to it as a basis for the conferment of the status of Citizenship. Furthermore, it outlines the right of

³¹ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/indigenouspeoples> accessed 25th June 2023.

³² Merriam–Webster’s Collegiate Dictionary 11 Edition, 634.

³³ United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People 2007.

³⁴ Joseph Dangam Rinyom, ‘Indigeneship, Citizenship, and the Lost Nigerianship’ An Unpopular Essay.

Nigerian citizens to be a part of any community or ethnic group and prohibits discrimination based on ethnicity.³⁵ Section 25 (1)(a) of the Constitution states as follows:

The following persons are citizens of Nigeria by birth namely: “*Every Person born in Nigeria before the date of independence, either of whose parents or any of whose grandparents belong or belonged to a community indigenous to Nigeria*”. The constitution does not clearly state the meaning of “a community indigenous to Nigeria. .In reality, Nigeria's 774 local government bodies (LGAs) establish a person's "indigeneity" by issuing certificates attesting to their membership in a community.³⁶ Sec 27(2) of the same constitution also provides for individuals who want to become Nigerians through the process of Naturalization and among other requirements mandates that such person be subject to, “*the opinion of the Governor of the State where he is or he proposes to be resident, acceptable to the local community in which he is to live permanently, and has been assimilated into the way of life of Nigerians in that part of the Federation*”, hence there is an emphasis for any Nigerian or would be Nigerian to be indigenous, *i.e.* belong to a local or indigenous community.

By the immediate provision above, a dichotomy is being made between residency and citizenship. A citizen by birth must be an indigene to a community in Nigeria while a citizen by naturalization is recognized based on residency. Their rights and obligations arising from the two are not the same. For instance, under section 131 of the Constitution, only a citizen by birth is qualified to contest the position of the President of Nigeria. Similarly, only a citizen by birth can be a Governor of the State as provided in section 177 (a) of the Constitution. In the same vein, one needs to be an indigene of a state to be appointed as a member of the Federal Executive Council representing that state in the Federal Cabinet as a Minister. The constitution emphatically provides thus: “Any appointment under subsection 2 of this section by the President shall be in conformity with the provisions of section 14(2) of this Constitution. Provided that in giving effect to the provisions of the aforesaid, the President shall appoint at least one Minister from each State, who shall be *an indigene* of that State.”³⁷

3.0.2. Federal Character Commission (Establishment) 1995

The Federal Character Commission (Establishment) Act is one of those legal instruments that seek to promote indigeneship entitlement in Nigeria. The Act established the Federal Character Commission to

³⁵ 1999 Constitution, s. 42.

³⁶ Bronwen Manby and Solomon Momoh, ‘Report on citizenship in Nigeria,’ RSCAS/GLOBALCIT-CR (2020/12), <https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/67855/RSCAS_2020_12.pdf?sequence=1> accessed 11 may 2023.

³⁷ 1999 Constitution, s. 147 (3).

promote, monitor, and enforce compliance with the principles of proportional sharing of all bureaucratic, economic, media, and political posts at all levels of government. It defines the composition,³⁸ functions, and powers of the commission.³⁹ Part II of the Act defined the word “indigene”. as follows:

1. *“An indigene of local government means a person.*

(a) either of whose parents or any of whose grandparents was or in an indigene of the local government concerned; or

(b) who is accepted as an indigene by the local government: Provided that no person shall lay claim to more than local government.

(2) An indigene of a state means a person who is an indigene of the local government in that state. Provides that no person shall lay claim to more than state or to state and the federal capital territory

(3) An indigene of the federal capital territory (a) is a Nigerian citizen, other by naturalization, who cannot lay claim to any state of the federation or

(b) is a person born in the federal capital territory and whose descendants lived in the area presently constituting the federal capital territory 26 February 1976 and has continued to reside in the federal capital territory after that date.

Section 2 of the subsidiary legislation deals with the position of married women. It states that “a married woman shall continue to lay claim to her State of origin for the purpose of implementation of the federal character formulae at the national level.”

From the foregoing provisions, it is clear that indigeneship can be claimed through two methods. The first is based on one's paternal origin or ancestry. According to this method, no one may claim to be an indigene unless they can prove that their parents or grandparents are indigenes of a specific place in Nigeria. The second strategy is predicated on assimilation and acceptance by the populace of any Nigerian locality. This strategy gives local governments the authority to choose whether Nigerians are considered indigenes. In Nigeria, this procedure of becoming an indigene seems to be more liberal and accommodating. However, the Act has failed to state the standards by which local governments should judge whether a person is an indigene of Nigeria or not. In a bid to create an equitable formula for the distribution of socio-economic services and establish modalities for redressing the problems of imbalances and reducing the inequality

³⁸ Federal Character Commission (Establishment) Act 1995, s. 2.

³⁹ Ibid, s. 4 & 5.

occasioned by deprivation and marginalization of any indigenous group in the country, the Commission is empowered to:

to work out- (i) an equitable formula, subject to the approval of the President, for distribution of socio-economic services, amenities and infrastructural facilities; (ii) modalities and schemes, subject to the approval of the President, for redressing the problems of imbalances and reducing the fear of relative deprivation and marginalization in the Nigerian system of federalism as it obtains in the public and private sectors;⁴⁰

To realize the optimal aims and objectives for the establishment of the Commission and the enactment of the Act, the functions of the Commission as expressly stated in section 4 must not only be carried out, but must be seen to have been carried out without fear or favour and by the letters and the spirit of the Act and its subsidiary legislation. Hence, the commission is to ensure that all public officers adhere strictly to rules and subsidiary legislation made pursuant to the Act as non-compliance with the guidelines issued or subsidiary legislation made particularly pursuant to paragraph (h) of subsection (1) of this section will amount to an offence and such a person who has failed to comply with the Act will be liable upon conviction to payment of fine in the sum of 50,000 or imprisonment for six months or both.⁴¹ In the same vein, the provision of section 16 of the Act establishes the supremacy of the Act and its provisions over any other enactment or laws in the entire country. The said section 16 is reproduced thus:

Subject to the Constitution, where any provision of this Act is inconsistent with the provisions of any other law or enactment, the provisions of this Act shall to the extent of that inconsistency prevail.

Going by the above provision of section 16 of the Act, where any other law or enactment of the National Assembly irrespective of how highly placed or important such Act may be, is inconsistent, offends, and/or contradicts the provision of the Federal Character Commission Act, the provision of the Act shall prevail and such law or enactment shall be declared to the extent of its inconsistency to the provision of the Act. Hence, the only law to which the Act is subjected is the Constitution.

3.0.3. Local Government Laws

⁴⁰ Ibid, s. 4

⁴¹ Ibid, s. 15(1)

Nigerian local government laws mandate the registration of indigenous people and non-indigenous people, as well as the distribution of resources based on indigenous status. As a result, non-indigenous people are sometimes refused access to important social services and opportunities, such as work and education. This is enforced by the issuance of indigeneship certificates by Local Government Authorities which is left at the discretion of officials and sometimes traditional rulers without any set criteria or opportunity for appeal of denial.

3.0.4. National Youth Service Corps Act

All Nigerian graduates must complete a one-year national service program under the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) Act.⁴² To promote national unity and integration, the Act also mandates that participants serve in states other than their state of origin. As a result, both the state where a person is from and their indigenous community will be taken into account during posting.

3.0. Examples of Discriminatory Tendencies of Indigeneship in Nigeria

The following are some discriminatory tendencies inherent in the application of indigeneship in Nigeria

3.0.1 Discriminatory Employment Opportunities:

Indigeneship recognition plays a crucial in determining who gets employed in civil and public service in Nigeria. Under the Federal Character Commission (Establishment) Act Nigerians must be “indigenes” to have access to certain employment opportunities at the federal, state, and local government levels. At state and local government levels employment opportunities are exclusively reserved for those who are regarded as indigenes. Many states often refuse to employ non-indigenes or settlers in their civil services. They also maintain that certain positions can only be filled by non-indigenes if indigenes are unable to take up the positions. Some states only employ non-indigenes on a contract or temporary basis only. Where there are no written laws to this effect there are unspoken rules about the employment of non-indigenes in government jobs. Some of these policies have been subjected to judicial scrutiny in several cases. In *Anzaku & 33 others v Governor of Nasarawa State*,⁴³ the Court of Appeal held that the Nasarawa state government policy to deploy all local government staff to their local government of origin was discriminatory and in breach of section 42 of the 1999 Constitution. The Court noted that section 42 of the Constitution not only prohibits all forms of discrimination on grounds of community or ethnic group, place of origin, sex, religion, or political opinion to which a citizen belongs but also forbids government actions

⁴² CAP 84 LFN 1990.

⁴³ (2005) 5 NWLR Pt. 919 at 484-485 CA.

that tend to create an obstacle to the enjoyment of fundamental rights and freedoms. The court further observed that the prohibitive language of section 42 is not limited to the express application of any law in force in Nigeria, but also to the practical application of any executive or administrative action of the government.

3.0.2 Inequitable Access to Land

In some states in Nigeria, access to land depends on whether or not someone is an indigene. Section 1 of the Land Use Act 1979 vests all the power and authority over land in the hands of the Governor of states. It states that subject to the provisions of this Act, all land comprised in the territory of each state of the federation shall be vested in the Governor of the state and shall hold such land trust and administered for the use and common benefit of the people.⁴⁴ Apart from the Act, the land tenure system in Nigeria also customary and communal ownership of land which in some is held in trust for the people by ethnic traditional rulers. In some localities, it is reported that traditional rulers restrict access to those lands to indigenes of the community. Most communities adopt this practice for fear of domination and invasion by other ethnic groups or communities.

3.0.3. Discriminatory Access to Bursary/Scholarship Awards

In most states in Nigeria, access to scholarship and bursary awards is exclusively reserved for indigenes. Non-indigenes are required to go home (their states), even when they may not have another home despite their contribution to the development of that state. In Lagos State, for example, access to bursary scholarships is restricted to indigenes of the State who are required to produce letters of identification from the Local Government where the candidate hails from and letters of identification from the appropriate traditional rulers/Oba as eligibility criteria.⁴⁵ A similar situation also exists in Ondo State where bursary and scholarship benefits are given to the indigenes of the state to the exclusion of other candidates who are citizens of other states though residing in the same states. According to the Ondo State Scholarship Board, a scholarship award of #100,000.00 shall be granted to each deserving student of Ondo State origin in Tertiary institutions in Nigeria undergoing HND and undergraduate degree courses⁴⁶.

⁴⁴ Land Use Act LFN 1990, s. 1.

⁴⁵ See Lagos State Scholarship Board Award Scheme <<https://scholarship-fellowship.com/lagos-state-undergraduate-scholarship-award-scheme/>> accessed 28 May 2023.

⁴⁶ Ondo State Scholarship Board <<https://onssb.ondostate.gov.ng/scholarship.html>> accessed 28 May 2023

3.0.4. Discriminatory Political Participation

Indigeneship recognition also influences political participation in most parts of Nigeria. While non-indigenes are legally able to vote in federal, state, and local government elections, they are usually not considered for elective positions at the state and level government levels. This is despite the fact there are no requirements related to ethnicity or indigeneship imposed by law on their right to contest for elective positions or hold a public office in any state in the federation. A non-indigene may vote but may find it very hard to run for elective office in the area where he or reside resides.

3.0.5. Discriminatory School Fees

In most states in Nigeria, the school fees that are payable in educational institutions are usually scheduled based on indigenes and non-indigenes. Indigenes are required to pay lesser fees than the non -indigenes or settlers. As a result, many of the non-indigenes are unable to continue and withdraw from their course of study due to the exorbitant amount of money that they are required to pay as school fees.

3.0.6. Inequitable Admission Policies and Guidelines

Admissions to secondary and higher institutions are also influenced by indigeneship status. Indigenes are given preference over non-indigenes, even when those indigenes are less qualified for admission. This particular practice promotes mediocrity and incompetence.

4.0. Effects of Indigeneship Recognition in Nigeria

The effects of indigeneship recognition include:

4.0.1. Threatens Tolerance and Peaceful Co-Existence

The promotion of indigeneship supremacy/soil of the soil mentality threatens tolerance and peaceful co-existence in society. Most commentators have argued that a lack of peaceful co-existence breeds disintegration, poverty, and underdevelopment among the people. It implicates national integration and the socio-economic development of the country. Many communities that experienced indigene-settler conflicts years back are yet to recover from the negative consequences of that crisis. Former President Olusegun Obasanjo succinctly highlighted this fact when he stated thus: *“Another destructive impact of this monstrous (referring to indigene-settler conflict) is that militates against the imperatives of the integration of national economy, which demands that men and capital must be allowed to move freely and*

grow whenever they choose."⁴⁷ Apart from socioeconomic impact, issues surrounding the indigeneship recognition have also led to the loss of many lives and properties in the country. For example, the Tiv-Jukun crisis that erupted in the year 2000/2001 resulted in the death of hundreds of people while many others were forced to flee their respective communities. The crisis led to the development of many refugee camps in both Benue State and Taraba State. The Bassa-Igbira-Gbagyi conflict in Nasarawa state is another obvious example of an indigene-settler rift in Nigeria. The conflict ensued sometime in 1986 among these three ethnic groups who laid claim to the same land as their ancestral heritage. This conflict has also led to the loss of so many lives and properties on all sides. Government must do everything possible to prevent these kinds of crises and address issues associated with indigeneship recognition to promote an egalitarian society where everybody can live peacefully without rancour or strife arising from attempts to assert indigeneship.

4.0.2. Promote Mediocrity and Incompetence

Mediocrity and incompetence are some of the banes of national development. They bring promote abuses corruption, inefficiency in public service administration, and national development. underdevelopment in society. In Nigeria, indigeneship is often used as a criterion to appoint people to public office rather than their technical capability and competence. This sentiment is always promoted by affiliation with one's local government or state of origin. The establishment of states and local governments within the Nigerian federal structure was done to promote national unity, cohesion, and national development. A federal state's fundamental objectives seem to be threatened by the continued emphasis on local government indigeneship certificates and certificates of state of origin as the basis for participation and contribution to national development through civil or public service administration. The issue of merit and competence is key to the economic, social, and political development of the country. It is interesting to note that while the Federal Character Commission (Establishment) Act attempts to promote indigeneship recognition as the basis for appointment into public service services of the federation, it has promoted merit and competence in the public service of the federation. The Act provides that the best and most competent persons shall be recruited from each state or the Federal Capital Territory.⁴⁸ It also states that once a candidate has

⁴⁷ Auwalu Musa and Yusuf Abdullahi, 'Federalism and National Integration: The Indigene/Settler Dichotomy' *Sokoto Journal of the Social Science* (2013) 3 (1) 57-71.

⁴⁸ Federal Character Commission (Establishment) Act, Part 1, s 2.

attained the necessary minimum requirement for appointment to a position, he shall qualify to fill a relevant vacancy reserved for indigenes of his state or the Federal Capital Territory.⁴⁹

4.0.3. Instrument for Divide and Rule by the Political Class

The political establishment is using the question of indigeneship as a “divide-and-rule” strategy. These pseudo-theocratic tendencies can be traced to the colonial administration during which the “ideology of tribalism” was propagated by British colonial masters to create division among the people they were met to govern and unite. Instead of strengthening inclusive governance, political elites in the country often engage in divisive tendencies to promote hatred, intolerance, and selfish political agenda under the guise of indigeneship. Many political elites have also explored divide-and-rule politics to promote polarization in the nation’s electioneering and democratic process, especially along ethnic, tribal, and religious lines.

4.0.4. Violate Democratic Ideas and Values.

Another implication of indigeneship recognition is that it impedes democratic ideals and values. It violates the principles of the rule of law and equality before the law. Indigeneship recognition is often exploited by people to promote disintegration and violates individual rights and freedoms. It violates the right to freedom from discrimination established to ensure that no citizen of Nigeria is discriminated against on the grounds of sex, place of origin, ethnic group, or religion.⁵⁰ The principle of non-discrimination is integral to the democratic system because it promotes equal participation, inclusiveness, cohesion, and social justice. It also ensures that individual interest and aspiration is adequately protected and secured.

4.0.5. Discourage National Integration and Unity.

The struggle for indigeneship recognition impedes national integration and unity. National integration and national unity mean two different things. National integration is the process through which different individuals and groups are brought together to promote peace and harmony in society. National unity, on the other hand, implies a situation whereby people of diverse cultures, religions, languages, and political, social, and economic systems are brought together to have a common goal. One of the objectives of a federal system such as Nigeria’s is the promotion of national integration and unity among the multi-ethnic nationalities that agreed to live together within a sovereign entity. It is interesting to note federalism is not

⁴⁹ Ibid, s. 3.

⁵⁰ 1999 Constitution, s. 42

just about the devolution of power between the central government and component units, but also the process of balance of power among the diverse ethnic/tribal groups. The concept of national integration and unity implies that people of different ethnic nationalities and backgrounds can live together without needless struggle for indigeneship recognition since the 1999 Constitution that establishes the federal structure of the country failed to define who an indigene is and the procedure for achieving same.

4.0.6. Impede Intergovernmental Relations and Competitive Federalism

The struggle for indigeneship recognition impedes intergovernmental relation and discourage competitive federalism between the federal, state, and local government. Competitive federalism is a constitutional concept that implies the existence and desirability of healthy competition among the various federating units within a federal system of government. It refers to the relationship between state government (horizontal competition) and between federal and state governments (vertical competition). The issue of indigeneship recognition is particularly implicated by the relationship that exists among the various federating units which may arise from incidences of indigene/settler conflict cutting across state boundaries and territories. Therefore, the government must take appropriate measures to checkmate the inordinate struggle for indigeneship supremacy with the potential to create distrust among states, stifle intergovernmental relationships and competitive federalism,

5.0. Recommendations and Conclusion

5.0.1. Conclusion

The paper has shown that the fundamental reasons why indigeneship or state of origin is reckoned with in Nigeria are to ensure that every segment of the country participates in the governance and also has its share of the national cake. However, in many cases, this practice works counterproductively in that it creates more division and inequality in the polity. A society that desires to thrive on peaceful coexistence, unity, and economic growth and progress must ensure that all its citizens are treated fairly and equally without undue discrimination based on indigeneship and settlers.

5.0.2. Recommendations.

The recommendations are as follows:

- i. The 1999 Constitution should be amended to include the definition of indigene and procedures for acquiring same. This definition must include the number of generations a family is expected to live in a state before its members become indigenes in that state.

- ii. The federal government should abrogate the “state of origin” idea and adopt a “state of residence”.
- iii. Both State and local governments must ensure that every citizen has access to public services, scholarships, and public infrastructure without any preference or discrimination given to indigenes or non-indigenes.
- iv. The Nigerian government should develop new economic opportunities to reduce poverty, unemployment, and youth restiveness capable of igniting tribal violence and indigene/settler rift.
- v. The National Orientation Agency must develop new radio and television programs and jingles to promote public awareness and educate the people about the need for peaceful coexistence and tolerance.
- vi. The Nigerian government should review the basic and secondary school curricula to incorporate lessons -on national integration, and national unity including ethnic, and religious tolerance in the country.